

MICROSTRUCTURE AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF HEMP ELEMENTARY FIBRES FOR COMPOSITE APPLICATIONS BY MICRO-COMPUTED TOMOGRAPHY AND DIGITAL IMAGE CORRELATION

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ABSTRACT

This manuscript presents a new approach to measure the cross sectional areas of elementary fibres using micro-computed tomography. The correct and accurate measurement of the area allows a correct characterization of the strength of the fibre. The accuracy and reliability of tomography was validated through the determination of cross-sectional areas of 3D-printed fibres at the micro level. Moreover, the non-linear behavior of elementary and technical hemp fibre samples were characterized, by combining standard tensile tests with a detailed full-field strain map at the micro scale during tensile loading.

1 INTRODUCTION

The hierarchical organization of hemp fibre composites can be characterized at 3 different levels: composite, technical fibre, and elementary fibre. At the composite level, the mechanical behaviour depends on the properties of the reinforcing fibre, the matrix and the fibre-matrix interface [1, 2]. However, natural fibres, such as hemp, are composite materials themselves showing a complex tensile behavior [3].

Technical natural fibres are being increasingly used as the reinforcing phase in long fibre reinforced composites. However, it is not clear whether the tensile behaviour of the technical fibre or the elementary fibre (or a combination of both) is predominant in order to predict the composite behaviour [3, 4]. Then it is crucial a correct determination of natural fibre mechanical properties at different levels.

This manuscript presents a new approach to measure the cross sectional areas of elementary fibres using micro-computed tomography. The correct and accurate measurement of the area allows a correct characterization of the strength of the fibre. The accuracy and reliability of tomography was validated through the determination of cross-sectional areas of 3D-printed fibres at the micro level. Moreover, the non-linear behavior of elementary and technical hemp fibre samples were characterized, by combining standard tensile tests with a detailed full-field strain map at the micro scale during tensile loading.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

In the framework of the FP7-MultiHemp project, 32 hemp fibre accessions were provided by partners of the consortium, and their mechanical properties analyzed. Two contrasting hemp samples, one with low and one with high technical fibre strength, were selected for analysis. Elementary fibres were extracted from these technical fibre samples. All samples were conditioned at 20° C and 50% RH for more than a month.

2.2 Strain Mapping

The fibre cross-sectional area was estimated using 3 methods:

- 1) fibres were weighed and the cross-sectional area of each individual fibre was calculated using its density, mass and length, assuming that fibres have a constant cross-section,
- 2) fibre diameter was measured by optical microscopy, also assuming that fibres have a constant cross-section, and
- 3) fibre cross-section was obtained using micro-tomography. A gauge length of 4 mm were used, with a crosshead speed of 0.5 mm/min.

A random speckle pattern was created on fibres by using an Airbrush with a spray nozzle of 0.15mm. In order to evaluate if the speckle patterns were good enough for digital image correlation (DIC) analysis, two methods were implemented: pixel intensity histogram and strain deviation analysis [3].

A Motic microscope SMZ-171-TH with a Moticam camera of 10 MP of resolution were used to acquire the images. A random speckle pattern was created on fibres by using an airbrush and a micro metal mesh. The speckle patterns quality was evaluated by the pixel intensity histogram and strain deviation methods [3]. Ncorr software was used for digital image correlation (DIC) analysis.

2.3 Tomography

A SkyScan micro computed tomography (microCT) device (Bruker microCT) for scanning electron microscope (SEM) was used for obtaining 3D images of elementary fibres.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Cross-Sectional Area

The cross-sectional areas of elementary fibres were compared to the results obtained to the more conventionally used weighing and diameter procedure for cross-sectional area determination. The areas acquired with tomography and weighing procedure corresponded well on the technical fibre level. Weighing of elementary fibres has been proven difficult due to the low mass of elementary hemp fibres, resulting in erroneous measurements.

On the other hand, diameter measurements for calculating the cross-sectional areas of technical and elementary hemp fibres were inaccurate due to the over- or underestimation of the cross-sectional area, depending on how the fibre was positioned during optical microscopy observation (Fig. 1).

3D reconstructions of the micro-computed tomography data demonstrated the irregular fibre structure and revealed that the assumption of a perfectly cylindrical elementary fibre is incorrect (Fig. 2). The tomography methodology provided accurate and reliable results for the determination of cross-sectional areas.

Fig.1 3D reconstructed elementary fibre (a), x-ray image of fibre at 0° position (b) and after a rotation of 90° (c).

Fig.2 Cross-sections of different elementary fibres.

3.2 Strain Mapping

The results showed that elementary fibres exhibit slightly higher strength values (~824 MPa and ~664 MPa, for the elementary fibres extracted from strong and weak samples respectively) but a marked higher apparent Young's modulus values measured by DIC analysis (~85 GPa and ~60 GPa for the elementary fibres extracted from strong and weak samples respectively, see Fig. 3) as their corresponding technical fibres [3].

Fig.3 Typical stress-strain and tangent Young's modulus-strain curves for a strong (a and b respectively) and a weak (c and d respectively) elementary fibre. Blue dots stand for strain obtained by the displacement of the tensile machine crosshead, orange dots indicate strain obtained by DIC analysis.

A correlation between the strength of a technical fibre and their elementary fibres was also observed. A clear difference in strength was observed for the strong and weak elementary fibres. Previous studies have primarily attributed the difference between strong and weak technical fibres to the role of the interphase between the elementary fibres only [3].

This study evinces that an elementary fibre extracted from a hemp accession with high strength also shows higher mechanical properties than an elementary fibre extracted from a technical fibre with lower strength. Also a lumen size dependence of the elementary fibre strength was observed.

In the longitudinal direction, elementary fibres exhibit a heterogeneous strain pattern. Bands of high strain are alternated with bands of lower strain perpendicular to the tensile axis (Fig. 4). This complex strain deformation pattern has also been observed for technical hemp fibres [3].

The elongation of fibres induces shear strain inside the cell wall between the cellulose microfibrils and the matrix around the microfibrils. This shear strain might be a consequence of the rotation of the microfibrils in the cell wall to an orientation which is nearly parallel to the fibre axis.

Fig.4 Full-field longitudinal and shear strain analysis for an elementary fibre. Strain maps represent the gradual evolution of local strain at 2 levels of global strain and the local strain distribution an instant before failure.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The analysis reveals a complex and very irregular pattern of strain concentrations which are associated to the elementary fibre strength. The non-linear behavior of the stress-strain curve is explained by the development of shear strain at the microfibril interphases.

This study also reveals that an elementary fibre extracted from a hemp accession with high strength also shows higher mechanical properties than an elementary fibre extracted from a technical fibre with lower strength.

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